

Effect of Doping with Mn and Mg Metals at Structural, Electrical and Dielectric Properties of BaTiO₃

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Abstract

BaTiO₃ was doped with manganese and magnesium elements at molar ratios of [0.01, 0.02 and 0.03M] in order to study and determine the effect of doping with these metals on the electrical conductivity and dielectric constant of the ceramic compound, which has a perovskite structure type. The samples were prepared by a solid state reaction after mixing the components and carrying out the calcination process at a temperature of 850°C. The preparation reaction was carried out at 850°C to form a powder of the doped compound. The samples were then pressed into circular discs under 7 tonnes of pressure, each of the samples was 1.8 cm in diameter and weighed 2 grams, these procedures were carried out simultaneously for all the prepared samples. The structural properties were studied using (Xrd Siemens model D500 diffractometer) the results has shown that the lattice constants are the same for all doping ratios approximately $a=b=4.01\text{\AA}$, $c=4.04\text{\AA}$ and the crystal structure is tetragonal belonging to space group P4mm. The results also showed that the Miller indices were approximately the same in all cases. The crystalline grains of the material were imaged and the morphological characteristics of the material were studied using a device (ZEISS model: Sigma VP) at the 200nm scale. It was found that the shape of the grains is almost spherical, with sizes ranging between 74 ~ 192.6nm, with some degree of porosity. Electrical conductivity and dielectric constant were measured using (GW Instek LCR-6000 Precision LCR Meter device), it was found that the electrical conductivity increased by a large percentage when the material was doped with manganese and magnesium, up to 783% when doped with 1%, and the dielectric constant decreased from 88.39 when the material was doped with 1% to 9.35 when the material was doped with 3%. The resistivity was also calculated and decreased inversely with increasing conductivity from $1.29 \times 10^7 (\Omega.m)$ to $4.89 \times 10^4 (\Omega.m)$ for the same doping level. As a result, the electrical conductivity properties improved and the dielectric properties of the doped material decreased.

Keywords: *Electrical conductivity, Resistivity, BTO, Single perovskite oxid.*

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Introduction

Barium Titanate Oxide (BTO) has been of practical interest for more than 60 years due to its attractive characteristics. First, because it is chemically and physically stable; second, because it shows ferroelectric properties at and above room temperature and third, because it is easily manufactured and used in the form of ceramic polycrystalline samples (Bhalla, Guo, & Roy, 2000). Barium titanate, characterised by its high dielectric constant and low loss properties, is utilised in applications such as capacitors and multilayer capacitors (MLCs). Doped barium titanate is extensively used in semiconductors, PTC thermistors, and piezoelectric devices, establishing actually as a significant ferroelectric ceramic. It belongs to the perovskite family, a substantial group of compounds. Ceramic materials with a perovskite structure are highly significant in electronics. This review paper presents an analysis of the barium titanate structure and the most commonly applied preparation methods (Vijatović, Bobić, & Stojanović, 2008). The natural crystal of solitary perovskite possesses many attractive physical features, including mechanical, optical, electrical, and structural characteristics. Mechanical properties include hardness ranging from 5.5 to 6 and density approximately between 4000 and 4300 kg/m³ while the optical properties, such as color, can transition from brown to black to grey, from brown to orange to yellow to white, and the refractive index of pure single perovskite is 2.38, and the structural properties verified that the crystal structure of this material is considered to be cubic, orthorhombic, and tetragonal (Tilley, 2016). Perovskite materials are applicable in various domains, including capacitors, multilayer capacitors, and solar cells, due to their chemical and mechanical stability, as well as their ease of preparation as polycrystalline samples (Vijatović, Bobić, & Stojanović, 2008). Barium titanate is the one of perovskite family which it has a chemical formula BaTiO₃. A lot of researchers have been studied the properties of barium titanate because it has good physical properties such as ferroelectric ceramics properties. It can be prepared by many methods like solid state reaction, sol gel, and hydrothermal reactions (Tanaka, 1954).

Materials and Experimental Procedures

We will employ solid state reaction as a method for sample preparation, and the basic compound in this doping process is BaTiO₃ which will substituted with Mg at the A site and Mn at the B site. The samples that were prepared adhered to the formula Ba(1-x) Mg x Ti(1-x) Mn xO₃, with x values of 0.01, 0.02, and 0.03. The subsequent steps were undertaken to prepare the three samples outlined below.

1. The initial step involves balancing the chemical equation as follows:

2. Prepare the new material [Ba(1-x) Mg x Ti(1-x) Mn xO₃] using four precursors: barium carbonate (BaCO₃) with a purity of 99.99%, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) with a purity of 99.99%, magnesium oxide (MgO) with a purity of 99.99%, and manganese dioxide (MnO₂) with a purity of 99.99%. Each of the samples has been measured with a highly accurate electronic balance. After weighing the components of each sample which was calculated based on the following equation (Nasiri, et al., 2023):

$$\text{weight (g)} = \text{Number of moles (N)} \times \text{Molecular weight (g/mol)} \quad (2)$$

they were placed in a mortar and mixed thoroughly with the addition of a few drops of acetone to form a cohesive mass. Subsequently, this mixture was emptied into a dish and then placed in an electric oven where the temperature was gradually increased by 25°C every five minutes until reaching 850°C for 10 hours. Upon completion of the specified duration, the oven was turned off, and the samples were allowed to cool, where the product was a grey powder. After cooling, the samples were taken to a hydraulic press, and each sample was pressed individually under a pressure of 7 tons, forming circular discs with a diameter of 1.8 cm, a thickness of 4 mm, and a weight of 2 grams per sample.

Characterization

X- Ray Characterization

The crystal structure for the created composite [Ba(1-x) Mg x Ti(1-x) Mn xO3] were be detected by (Xrd Siemens model D500 Diffractometer), by applying the following conditions: Scan Axis type is (Gonio), Start Position 2θ = (20.0400°), End Position 2θ= (79.9900°), Step Size 2θ = (0.0500), Scan Step Time =(1.0000) s, Scan Type :Pre-set time, Goniometer Radius (240mm), Measurement Temperature =(25°C), Anode Material is Cu, K-Alpha, wave length λ=(1.54060 Å).

SEM and EDX

Sem imaging was done by (ZEISS model: Sigma VP), edx were done by (EDS and mapping: Oxford instruments. UK) instrument.

Electrical Conductivity and Dielectric Constant

were be measured and detected by (GW Instek LCR-6000 Precision LCR Meter for conductivity and dielectric constant) instrument.

Results and Discussion

X-Ray Analysis

At the room temperature X-ray diffraction pattern (Fig.1) as Table.1 displays structural information for BaTiO₃ and Ba(1-x) Mg x.Ti(1-x).MnxO₃, which confirm the single phase tetragonal Barium Titanate structure. All peaks are identified as tetragonal BaTiO₃ in space group P4mm at some special peaks (110)(111)(210)(220)(211). Lattice parameters of BaTiO₃ were refined to a = b = 4.01Å, c= 4.04Å and lattice constants of Ba(1-x) Mg x.Ti(1-x).Mn were refined to a = b = 4.01Å, c= 3.99Å and a = b =4.01Å, c = 4.00Å and reported value of a = b = 3.994Å, c= 4.033Å. Lattice parameters (a, b, c) were calculated by using $[\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{h^2+k^2}{a^2+b^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2}]$ formula ,since a=b, (hkl) was generated by X-Ray characterization and d (Lattice spacing) was calculated by using bragg's-law. All above results confirmed that pure BTO and doped BTO has the same crystal structure which means that the adding of some impurities to composites do not change its main structure as found in study of Al-Ameri, Ahmed, & Babikier, (2020).

Table 1. Showing the Lattice Constants for Pure and Impure BaTiO₃

X (Molar fraction of Mg & Mn)	a(Å)	b(Å)	c(Å)	c/a(Å)
0	4.01	4.01	4.04	1

0.01	4.01	4.01	3.99	0.995
0.02	4.01	4.01	4.00	0.997
0.03	3.994	3.994	4.033	1

Figure 1. Shows XRD Pattern for Doped BTO with Different Molar Fraction of (Mn, Mg) Metals

FESEM Analysis

Figure 2. FESEM Images for Doped BTO at 200nm Scale:(a)1% Mn, Mg (b) 2% Mn, Mg (c) 3% Mn, Mg

According to Figure.2 (a) FESEM images for doped BTO 1% of (Mg, Mn metals) at 200nm scale where it has a semispherical shape for crystals and tend to have a nano-cumulative grain size with some regions and smaller sizes with the other. As the crystalline size is about 74 ~ 163 nm, this little variation of grains length may lead to form a rough surface. FESEM picture is clearly seen to have some porosity which indicates a higher dielectric constant for the base material(BaTiO₃). Figure.2(b) shows FESEM image for 2% doped BTO 200nm scale where we can see a clumps forming a semispherical shape because of the preparation method (solid state reaction) that clumps represents the crystal grains of doped BTO which have a various size (74~155nm) and have a little number of pores which indicates a less rough surface. The crystalline aggregates can be seen that divided to white part and gray part are linked together and that is due to the interaction of the dopants with the base material(BaTiO₃). The shape of the grains is almost the same for all 1%, 2% BTO samples, and even for 3%BTO as shown in Fig.2(c) which shows the FESEM image of the surface features, since we used the same (base material, dopant, temperature, duration, preparation method) for all samples. Crystalline size ranges 74~192.6nm. In addition sample 3 having a pores between grains more than samples 1and 2 and that results is similar to the study of (Chávez, et al., 2010).

Conductivity, Resistivity and Dielectric Constant Analysis

Adding the impurities to some materials usually leads to an increase in electrical conductivity and to explain this phenomenon, the following points can be taken in consideration: When a material is doped with the metallic elements, new atoms are introduced that carry free electrons (in the case of conductors) or holes (in the case of semiconductors), these electrons or holes act as additional charge carriers, increasing electrical conductivity due to the increased number of charge carriers (Hashem, & Haider, 2023). Metals usually contain valence electrons that move freely in the crystal lattice. When these atoms are introduced into a certain material, they contribute to improving the conduction of electrons by modifying the electronic structure by providing additional energy levels or facilitating the transfer of electrons through the material (Ben, et al., 2022). Doped metal atoms contribute to reducing obstacles to the movement of electrons in the material, which leads to reducing resistance and thus increasing the electrical conductivity of the material. It is possible to observe the electrical conductivity of the BTO compound before and after doping with Mn and Mg metals, we can see that the conductivity is small for the pure BTO compound, but it increases by a large percentage when doping by 1% with Mn and Mg metals, as the increase in electrical conductivity continues when the amount of doping is increased to 2% and even 3%. Figure.3(a) shows the relation between σ and impurities ratio. Based on the above, it can be said that the electrical conductivity has increased due to the increase in the number of charge carriers (free electrons) notice Table.2, as well as due to the generation of additional energy levels when the material is doped with the metallic elements.

Table 2. Electrical Properties for (1%, 2%, 3%) Doped BTO with Manganese and Magnesium

Doping ratio with Mn and Mg	Chemical formula	Dielectric Constant (Measured at 100 kHz)	Conductivity σ (A.C current) (S/m)	Resistivity ($\rho = 1/\sigma$) ($\Omega.m$)
0%	BaTiO ₃	-	7.7×10^{-8}	1.29×10^7
1%	Ba _{0.99} Mg _{0.01} .Ti _{0.99} Mn _{0.01} O ₃	88.39	68×10^{-8}	1.47×10^6
2%	Ba _{0.98} Mg _{0.02} .Ti _{0.98} Mn _{0.02} O ₃	67.60	174.9×10^{-7}	5.71×10^4
3%	Ba _{0.97} Mg _{0.03} .Ti _{0.97} Mn _{0.03} O ₃	9.35	204.4×10^{-7}	4.89×10^4

Figure 3. (a) Electrical Conductivity for Doped BTO at (0%,1%,2%,3%) mn and mg, (b) Electrical Resistivity for Doped BTO, (c) Measured Dielectric Constant(at 100 kHz) Versus Doping Ratio

Electrical resistivity as in Table.2 was calculated as an inverse function of the electrical conductivity as this work conclude (Erhart, & Albe, 2008). Since the BTO compound is ceramic, it has a large electrical resistivity Figure.3(b) and this resistivity is also affected by the size of the crystal grains and the porosity of the material, but it is inversely proportional to the amount of doping with metals, as it decreased significantly with the increase in the magnitude of both manganese and magnesium elements in the structure as with study of Hreniak, et al. (2006). Figure.3(c) shows the dielectric constant values change with impurities percent increases. When a certain compound is doped with a metal, the dielectric constant changes based on several factors related to the properties of the doped material and the nature of the doped metal. The explanation for this change depends on several factors, the first of which is doping, as doping with a metal can change the electronic distribution within the material, and if doping leads to an increase in the polarity of the material, this increases the ability to store charge, which leads to a higher dielectric constant as in this study (More, et al., 2021). Moreover, doping reduces polarity or distorts the distribution of charges, this may lead to a reduction in the dielectric constant. In addition, the presence of metal atoms may introduce new energy levels or modify the chemical bonds between the atoms of the substance, where this change can affect the dynamics of the material's response to the electric field and thus

affect the dielectric constant. If doping with a particular metal results in a significant increase in electrical conductivity, the material may become more energy loss, negatively affecting the dielectric constant by decreasing. Although frequency is one of the factors affecting the dielectric constant, in this work the frequency was fixed at 100 Hz when measuring the dielectric constant, so it cannot be said that it was affected by frequency on the other hand decreases in the dielectric constant with the increase in the doping rate (1%, 2%, 3%) with the metallic elements Mn and Mg Table.2 cannot be attributed to the change in electronic distribution nor to the increase in polarity, but on the contrary it can be said that the polarity has decreased significantly, which in turn led to a decrease in the dielectric constant. Likewise, the increase in the electrical conductivity rate is a major reason for the decrease in the dielectric constant of the impure structure agree with study (Bisen, Mishra, & Jarabana, 2016).

Conclusions

Barium titanate oxide is considered of great importance in electronic applications, especially in manufacturing of different types of capacitors, because of its ability to storage energy, and its low dielectric loss. It is also used in the manufacture of electronic sensors, for this reason, attention was paid to studying this material. In this work, the effect of doping on electrical conductivity and dielectric constant properties was studied. In this work, the effect of doping on the crystal structure of the compound was first studied. The results concluded that the crystal structure was not affected by doping at different concentrations, as the lattice constants were almost equal for all doping ratios, and the phase was tetragonal perovskite type. Electrical conductivity increased with the increase of manganese and magnesium by 783% when doping with 1%, as the resistivity decreased significantly with a decrease in the dielectric constant. The maximum conductivity obtained was 204.4×10^{-7} S/m and the lowest dielectric constant was about 9.35 at a constant temperature degree 850°C at 0.03doping ratio. This pointing the possibility of using this material in PTC thermistors and piezoelectric devices.

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